
Lived Experiences of Hospitalized Persons with Visual Disability

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ABSTRACT

Multiple studies indicate that many people worldwide face significant disabilities, often requiring specialized healthcare. However, little is known about the hospital experiences of Filipinos with visual disabilities. The study aimed to explore the lived experiences of hospitalized individuals with visual disabilities, addressing the challenges experienced by hospitalized persons with visual disabilities in the areas of accessibility and their adaptation to the hospital. Descriptive phenomenology was employed from 10 participants in Baguio City, La Trinidad, and Tuba, Benguet, Philippines, from January to May 2024, selected using purposive and referral sampling. In-depth, semi-structured interviews were conducted, and data were analyzed using Colaizzi's seven-step method. Three major themes with 12 sub-themes emerged from the participants' narratives, mainly: 1) Traveling through unfamiliar paths, (2) Connecting with carers, and (3) Adapting to healing. Hospitalized individuals with visual disabilities face challenges like inaccessible pathways, lack of aids, and service delays. Their treatment varies, with positive interactions involving care and prompt attention and negative ones involving neglect, long waits, and inappropriate behavior. The study revealed that hospitalized individuals with visual disabilities encountered challenges such as stereotypes, facility barriers, and admission delays

alongside positive experiences. Despite these, they demonstrated resilience through coping strategies, and their experiences were significantly influenced by the type of hospital.

This study highlights systemic barriers faced by visually disabled patients, emphasizing the need for improved accessibility, inclusive healthcare policies, and humanistic practices. Findings advocate policy enforcement, structural adaptations, sensitivity training, and patient empowerment to ensure equitable, inclusive care.

Keywords: Accessibility, barriers, healthcare, navigation, visual disability

INTRODUCTION

Globally, approximately 1.3 billion people experience significant disabilities, with sensory impairments, particularly visual disabilities, affecting 2.2 billion individuals (WHO, 2023). In the Philippines, visual disabilities affect an estimated 500,000 individuals (Robredo, 2018), while around 1.4 million households reported disabilities in 2010 (Institute for Labor Studies). Visual disability, characterized by reduced visual capacity that cannot be corrected through conventional means, significantly impacts daily life and healthcare access. Despite the existence of laws like the Magna Carta for Disabled Persons (Republic Act 7277, 1992) and initiatives such as the Department of Social Welfare and Development's Comprehensive Program for Persons with Disabilities, barriers persist for visually disabled individuals in accessing equitable and appropriate healthcare in the country.

The challenges faced by visually disabled individuals are not merely medical but also systemic and societal. Studies in high-income countries, such as those by Morse et al. (2019) and Binder-Olibrowska et al. (2022), emphasize the need for accessible hospital environments, including Braille signage, voice announcements, and well-designed pathways to prevent injuries. Furthermore, the psychosocial competencies of healthcare providers, such as communication skills, empathy, and disability awareness, are critical for fostering a patient-centered approach.

However, most of these studies are limited to high-income nations, leaving a gap in understanding how these issues manifest in low- and middle-income countries like the Philippines.

The current Philippine healthcare system, though supported by laws such as the Accessibility Law (Batas Pambansa Blg. 344, 1982) and RA 9442, lacks comprehensive implementation to address the unique needs of hospitalized persons with visual disabilities. Issues such as inadequate infrastructure, lack of trained medical personnel, financial constraints, and transportation challenges exacerbate the healthcare inequities experienced by this population (Pedron, 2018; Reyes et al., 2018). These barriers often result in poorer clinical outcomes and significant financial strain for hospitalized individuals with severe visual disabilities (Harris & Wright, 2021). Yet, research into their lived experiences remains scarce, particularly in the Philippine context.

This study seeks to bridge knowledge gaps and better understand how healthcare services in the Philippines meet the needs of visually disabled patients during hospitalization. By exploring the unique challenges faced by this population, the research aims to highlight gaps in current laws and healthcare practices, offering actionable recommendations for improving care quality. It seeks to raise awareness of the lived experiences of hospitalized individuals with visual disabilities and advocate for reforms that prioritize their dignity, rights, and well-being. The study will identify and critically analyze barriers to healthcare access for visually disabled individuals. It will provide insights into how existing laws, services, and hospital practices address their needs, ultimately contributing to a more inclusive healthcare system based on equity and accessibility for all.

METHODOLOGY

This qualitative study delves into the hospitalization experiences of individuals with visual impairments, emphasizing their unique challenges and coping mechanisms. Guided by descriptive phenomenology, the research sought to capture participants' lived experiences in real-world contexts, underscoring the

profound and diverse realities shaped by their social interactions, family dynamics, and socio-educational backgrounds. The study adhered to Streubert and Carpenter's (2007) qualitative research principles, incorporating in-depth, semi-structured interviews to foster open dialogue. Before data gathering, an endorsed proposal was submitted by the technical panel to the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of SLU. A total of ten participants, aged 27–69 and residing in Baguio City, La Trinidad, and Benguet, were selected using purposive and snowball sampling. Inclusion criteria ensured relevance, with data collection ceasing upon saturation. Participants were interviewed in comfortable, distraction-free environments, such as homes, cafés, or workplaces. The interviews, lasting 30–60 minutes, explored their challenges with hospital accessibility, adaptation to structural designs, and coping strategies.

Colaizzi's seven-step phenomenological process guided the meticulous transcription, coding, and thematic analysis of the data. Member-checking and iterative team discussions ensured accuracy, validity, and alignment with participant narratives. Credibility was ensured through prolonged engagement, bracketing, and transparent audit trails to establish trustworthiness. Dependability was achieved by fostering consistent collaboration among researchers and incorporating feedback from research panelists. Confirmability was maintained through reflexivity, peer debriefing, and member validation of findings. Transferability was enhanced by including rich participant quotations and non-verbal cues in the analysis. Ethical considerations were central to the research process. Informed consent was obtained through accessible means, including one-on-one discussions and thumbprint acknowledgments. The researchers addressed participants' vulnerability with empathy and ensured privacy, confidentiality, and equitable treatment. Participants were reimbursed for any costs incurred during the study to ensure fairness. Findings highlighted the participants' difficulties navigating hospital systems, the importance of support systems, and their resilience in coping with these challenges. The study's insights contribute to a deeper understanding of visually impaired individuals' healthcare experiences, providing a foundation for policymakers to develop inclusive healthcare guidelines. This

research underscores the value of amplifying marginalized voices, fostering inclusivity, and ensuring equitable access to healthcare services for all.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the findings and discussions of the study, in which ten people shared their rich experiences about the phenomenon under investigation. The information acquired led to the development of three major themes and twelve sub-themes, as shown in Figure 1.

MAIN THEME 1: TRAVELING THROUGH UNFAMILIAR PATHS

Traveling through unfamiliar paths refers to the difficulties that hospitalized persons with visual disabilities face in navigating the hospital's physical environment. These difficulties stem from various factors, such as inaccessibility of pathways, lack of visually assistive devices, and inability to adapt to new environments.

Subtheme 1.1. Movements limited by barriers

The subtheme captures the challenges visually impaired patients face in accessing hospital amenities like restrooms, nurses' stations, and wards. Factors such as distant facilities, unorganized layouts, obstacles, and limited space exacerbate these difficulties.

The participants' experiences reveal that inaccessible facilities and poor layout hinder hospital navigation, resulting in unmet physiological needs such as urination, shelter, and health care. Maslow's hierarchy of needs emphasizes that these basic needs must be met before higher-level needs can be addressed. Binder-Olibrowska et al. (2022) highlight that proximity and unobstructed pathways are essential for visually impaired patients to fulfill these fundamental needs.

Additionally, participants without caregivers present relied heavily on hospital staff for assistance. Guerreiro et al. (2019) and Morse et al. (2019) corroborate these findings, stating that

visually impaired individuals often depend on hospital staff to navigate inaccessible facilities and avoid potential injuries.

Figure 1. Themes and subthemes emerged from the lived experiences of hospitalized persons with visual disability

They also struggle with unfamiliar layouts, inaccessible features, and a lack of orientation cues like landmarks, tactile markings, or sounds. Consistency in layout and orientation skills, such as identifying signs or landmarks, is essential for independent navigation. Bahtiyar & Can (2021) emphasized this need, stating that obstacles and random layouts exacerbate the difficulties faced by blind individuals.

They also find it difficult to adapt to the hospital environment despite prior orientations provided by the staff. For instance, orange acknowledges that she needs assistance from the hospital staff to navigate the facilities.

ORANGE: "Pag talagang kung baguhan kami kahit ituro nila, mahirap din para sa amin parin yun. Kasi, simple, uhhh bago kami sa lugar na yun, hindi rin namin

kasi kaagad makabisado, kaya kailangan talaga namin na doon yung talagang mag-a-assist talaga..."

(When we're new to the place, even if they orient us, it's still difficult for us. Because we're new to that place, we don't immediately memorize it, so we really need someone to assist us there.)

Jeamwatthanachai et al. (2018) support this, noting that visually impaired individuals often lack confidence in navigating new environments due to limited reliance on sighted guides and unfamiliarity with typical landmarks.

The challenges of navigating inaccessible hospital facilities highlight an urgent need for improvement. Long distances, disorganized layouts, and obstacles lead to unmet needs, dependency on staff, and difficulty adapting to environments. According to Binder-Olibrowska et al. (2022), accessibility is vital to ensure patient safety, autonomy, and dignity. Addressing these barriers fosters inclusivity, independence, and equal access to healthcare for visually impaired patients.

Subtheme 1.2. Walking paths void of aids

Walking paths void of aids highlight the absence of assistive devices or features intended to help visually disabled individuals navigate safely and independently around the hospital environment. A visually assistive device is any tool, equipment, software, or product system that helps individuals maintain or enhance their functional abilities. (Braille Institute Staff, 2020). These are devices that aid in mobility, navigation, and reading (Blind/Visual Impairment: Common Assistive Technologies, 2023). Visually assistive devices in hospitals include canes, hand railings, and braille displays.

Some participants expressed that they did not observe any visually assistive devices in the hospital, specifically along the pathways leading to the comfort rooms. The absence of handrails in the ward prevented them from independently navigating to the comfort room. These findings highlight a lack of visually assistive devices like handrails and signage in hospitals. Jafaar et al. (2023) emphasize that handrails are essential in public hospi-

tals for persons with disabilities, providing stability, preventing falls, and aiding navigation on slippery surfaces.

The lack of visually assistive devices in hospitals creates challenges for visually disabled individuals, limiting their ability to navigate safely. Handrails and signage are essential for accessibility, as they provide stability and direction. Addressing this gap is critical to promoting inclusivity and safety in hospital settings, allowing all patients to navigate independently and confidently.

MAIN THEME 2: CONNECTING WITH CARERS

Connecting with carers refers to the vital relationship between visually impaired individuals and their caregivers and healthcare professionals within the healthcare environment. A carer provides physical, emotional, and practical care and support to visually impaired patients, helping them navigate hospital settings, meet daily needs, and adapt to healthcare environments.

Subtheme 2.1. Caring nature that nurtures

The hospital staff's caring nature, including compassion, reliability, and support, greatly enhances the well-being of visually disabled patients. This tailored care, along with caregiver involvement, improves the hospital experience.

Fakoya et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of compassionate staff, supported by Bentum-Micah et al. (2020), who found empathy improves patient outcomes. Moudatsou et al. (2020) highlighted how a person-centered approach fosters empathy and acceptance in clinical settings. Participants valued effective communication and compassionate care, as polite, respectful communication fostered comfort and satisfaction. These findings stress the importance of empathy in improving healthcare outcomes.

Ravaghi et al. (2020) noted that proximity to nurses improves monitoring and emergency response, highlighting the role of facility layout in patient experience. This is reflected in some of the participants' experiences, in which they were initially placed near the nurses' station for easy communication.

Caregivers also play a crucial role in supporting visually impaired patients by assisting with navigation and daily needs. Mashiata et al. (2022) and Ejiakor et al. (2019) emphasized that caregiver assistance improves comfort, quality of life, and access to healthcare services. These findings show that caregivers enhance the hospital experience by supporting patients with tasks and ensuring comfort during hospitalization.

Subtheme 2.2. Prompt attention by health professionals

This subtheme highlights the importance of healthcare professionals' responsiveness to the specific needs of visually disabled patients, including timely medication, prompt assistance, and proactive health management. The quality of care directly affects the well-being and satisfaction of these patients, emphasizing the importance of attentive and responsive healthcare services.

Participants shared positive experiences with prompt assistance upon arrival at the hospital. Nurses quickly attended to them, explained the process, and ensured timely care, with some receiving immediate diagnostic tests. Tools like buzzers were provided to request help, and staff responded efficiently, reflecting the hospital's commitment to patient needs. These experiences align with findings by Cassarino et al. (2021), which highlight that early healthcare intervention can reduce hospital stays.

The participants also highlighted the frequent and regular visits they received from the nurses and doctors. This experience shows that regular and attentive healthcare can significantly impact patient satisfaction and outcomes, aligning with the principles outlined in the Donabedian Model of Healthcare Quality. The level of regular care not only provided necessary medical attention but also offered reassurance during a critical time.

The finding suggests that consistent and proactive healthcare practices contribute significantly to the overall well-being and reassurance of visually disabled individuals during hospitalization. Moreover, it emphasizes the importance of healthcare providers' responsiveness and availability in meeting

the unique healthcare needs of visually disabled patients, ultimately enhancing the quality of care provided.

Subtheme 2.3 Inappropriate behavior and communication style

Inappropriate behavior and communication styles refer to the hospital staff's actions or speech that convey unclear engagement, unprofessionalism, disinterest, or lack of respect, which hinder patients' participation in care plans, weaken their dignity, and impede their ability to express their feelings and concerns.

Patients with visual disabilities experienced stress, discomfort, and aggravated medical conditions due to perceived neglect from hospital staff, resulting from poor communication and medical attention. Surachman and Almeida (2018) emphasized that neglect can trigger physiological and psychological stress responses, such as increased heart rate and anxiety, which can jeopardize health and well-being. It also impacts their safety needs, which are crucial for overall well-being and align with Maslow's second tier of needs (McKay, 2021). Unmet safety needs can heighten anxiety and frustration, negatively affecting their health (Mcleod, 2024).

The participants also experienced indirect communication from hospital staff, which may have overlooked the capabilities and intelligence of visually disabled individuals, creating a barrier to direct engagement and empowerment. A study revealed that healthcare professionals often neglect the needs of visually disabled individuals due to indirect communication, frequently focusing on companions or caregivers (Kwame & Petrucka, 2021).

Poor communication among healthcare professionals leads to miscommunication and dismissive attitudes, affecting patients' sense of safety, belonging, and trust, as per Maslow's hierarchy of needs. Studies by Olkin et al. (2019) and Jackson et al. (2019) show that these issues, along with ableist biases, delay diagnosis and create care inequities, resulting in subpar service. Inappropriate healthcare behavior towards visually impaired patients exacerbates stress and worsens medical conditions. Addressing these communication issues is essential for improving

health outcomes and meeting patients' needs. Healthcare systems must train staff to support visually impaired patients better, fostering a more inclusive environment.

Subtheme 2.4. Enduring long wait for a helping hand

This subtheme highlights the challenges visually disabled individuals face in healthcare, where long waiting times persist despite their priority status. The gap between their recognized priority and inadequate care reflects a systemic failure to address their unique needs, resulting in delays in diagnostics, procedures, treatments, and medication.

According to Binder-Olibrowska et al. 2022, although high-quality healthcare for PWDs is a legislative goal, the diverse needs of specific disabilities, including visual disability, are often overlooked, as demonstrated in Beige's experience:

BEIGE: *“Hinihintay ko pong may lumapit kasi nasa... medyo nasa dulo po ako eh— sa may bintana. No choice hintayin talaga. Kasi wala naman ano— medyo malayo kasi.”*

(I'm waiting for someone to approach me because I'm... kind of at the end— by the window. I have no choice but to wait. Because there's no... it's quite far.)

The participants' experiences highlight the neglect in accommodating visually disabled individuals in healthcare facilities, where their basic personal care needs are inadequately addressed despite their vulnerability and urgent medical concerns. Their account underscores physical barriers, such as being positioned away from main areas, hindering access to timely assistance.

Patients often experience frustration and dissatisfaction due to prolonged waiting times and inadequate attention during hospitalization. Studies, such as McIntyre and Chow's (2020), highlight the negative impact of delayed treatments on patient satisfaction, clinical outcomes, and patient anxiety. Delays in care reflect the importance of timely healthcare access, as outlined in Maslow's hierarchy of needs. Addressing these delays is crucial for improving patient experiences and outcomes. Reduc-

ing waiting times can enhance trust in healthcare services, improve clinical results, and optimize care delivery.

Subtheme 2.5. Lapses in care that are avoidable

Lapses in care refer to mistakes or gaps in medical care, such as missed medications, delayed treatments, procedural errors, and inadequate monitoring or instructions. These lapses compromise patient safety, increase risks, and may lead to complications. Addressing them requires thorough, attentive care and streamlined healthcare access to ensure optimal outcomes.

Some of the participants experience a care gap marked by communication breakdowns and coordination failures in the healthcare system. For instance, Baby Blue expressed frustration and confusion over her surgery's rescheduling. She mentioned that the internal medicine department failed to communicate her scheduled surgery to the operating room.

BABY BLUE: “Yung resched ng operasyon ko. Yung IM internal medicine hindi niya nasabi doon sa operating room na February 21 ang operasyon ko sana hindi pala nainform doon sa uhh operating room. Ang tagal namin naghintay buti sana kung sinabi kaagad. Yun ang sinabi na— hindi wala wala ka naman pangalan dun sa operating room... yun kaya niresched.”

(My operation was rescheduled. The IM, the internal medicine, didn't mention in the operating room that my operation was scheduled for February 21. It seems like the operating room wasn't informed. We waited for so long; it would have been better if they had informed us right away. That's what they said—that my name wasn't mentioned in the operating room... that's why it was rescheduled.)

Hildegard Peplau's Interpersonal Relations Theory emphasizes effective communication between healthcare providers and patients, which is crucial for sharing information like surgery scheduling. Sharkiya (2023) further supports this, stating that communication builds trust and fosters a therapeutic relationship between providers and patients.

In addition, some participants often experience multiple punctures during blood extraction procedures, with staff struggling to locate veins. This leaves them feeling vulnerable and lacking control over the procedures. The repeated attempts at venous access highlight instances of inappropriate treatment, leading to unmet basic physiological needs. According to the Journal of Infusion Nursing (2020), multiple needle insertions can cause discomfort, reduce satisfaction, and increase the risk of venous depletion and infection. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs also suggests that repeated medical procedures negatively impact a patient's physiological well-being by inducing pain, discomfort, and potential complications.

MAIN THEME 3: ADAPTING TO HEAL

Adaptive healing refers to the strategies employed by hospitalized individuals with visual disabilities to navigate and manage their experiences effectively. These techniques include leveraging auditory perception for environmental navigation, drawing on faith for emotional support, using alternative adaptation and distraction methods, maintaining a positive outlook, and expressing emotions constructively.

Subtheme 3.1. Hearing as a basic sense

Hearing as a primary sense refers to the fundamental sensory experience of sound perception that plays a crucial role in adapting to the environment. In this context, individuals with visual disability rely on auditory cues to gather information about their surroundings and communicate with others to accommodate their needs. For instance, when their caregiver is unavailable, Violet relies on hospital staff to assist her with her needs, especially when it comes to using the restroom. However, she hesitates to ask for assistance because she can hear that the hospital staff are occupied with other tasks. As a result, she relies on her sense of hearing to determine whether the staff is ready to assist her.

VIOLET: *“Kung sakali na ano, ma ah... ihing ihi ka talagang ah... kasi maririnig naman kag- busy sila talagang parang mahiya ka mag ano ngay magsabi ng pasuyo.”*

(If ever, um... you really need to urinate because you can hear that they are busy. It's like you feel ashamed to ask for assistance.)

These experiences highlight the importance of auditory cues for visually disabled individuals in hospitals. According to Salih et al. (2022), sound is the primary source of information for the visually disabled, helping them navigate their environment and compensate for vision loss. Kolarik et al. (2020) also noted that loss of vision increases reliance on hearing for awareness, safety, communication, and interaction. Recognizing and addressing this reliance on auditory cues is crucial for ensuring the safety, autonomy, and well-being of visually impaired patients in healthcare settings.

Subtheme 3.2. Exercising one's faith

Exercising one's faith refers to using religion or other spiritual beliefs and practices to find strength and comfort. Thus, expressing reliance on prayer and seeking strength from God to endure difficult situations related to the challenges experienced during hospitalization.

The participants express their reliance on prayer by seeking strength from God to endure their situations. Thus, the findings show how faith can help them cope with difficulties faced at different points of their hospitalization. Challenges such as having no watcher present or a delay in admission despite having an emergency prompted the exercise of prayer as a coping strategy, especially if the participants cannot seek help from anyone. In relation to this, the study of Tshuma et al. (2022) highlights how visually disabled individuals turn to religion, faith, and belief in God to cope with the loss of their vision. Praying and seeking spiritual guidance is a form of support that offers comfort during difficulty. For many, faith is a beacon of hope, reminding them they are not alone. Engaging in religious practices and rituals can provide strength, resilience, and the ability to face the uncertainties associated with visual impairment.

Subtheme 3.3. Utilizing alternative techniques to cope

Utilizing alternative techniques to cope refers to the unique and personalized adjustments of hospitalized individuals

with visual disabilities to accommodate their needs and navigate the hospital setting effectively and independently. These techniques can also be applied to cope with boredom or inappropriate staff when undergoing checkups, interviews, and other procedures. These coping strategies or self-distraction techniques pertain to engaging in activities or other exercises to divert attention away from stress, perceived discomforts, or challenges faced during hospitalization.

One example of an alternative technique used is Blue's practice of counting steps and other beds in the ward.

BLUE: *“Parang tinansya ko, kung ilang.. beds.. yung pagitan.. yung bed ko sa CR para alam ko kung ilang beds o ilang hakbang ang gagawin ko para marating ko yung CR.”*

(I estimated the number of beds between my bed and the bathroom to determine how many I would need to pass or how many steps I needed to take to reach the bathroom.)

Due to the lack of assistive devices, Blue devised a plan to count steps and beds from his bed to facilities like the comfort room, allowing him to navigate independently when unaccompanied. His unique method of counting steps and beds stood out among participants. Kuriakose et al. (2022) emphasized the role of landmarks in navigation, while Sim (2020) noted that visually impaired individuals create personalized strategies to adapt. This approach highlights his ability to enhance autonomy despite limited accessibility, underscoring the importance of such strategies in promoting independence in healthcare setting.

Some participants used techniques like listening to music, talking to their watcher, and using humor to distract from boredom and anxiety during their hospital stay. Music therapy improves mood, pain, and anxiety (Tan et al., 2020), while Peplau's Interpersonal Theory highlights emotional support and coping strategies. Humor also helped participants manage rude comments or discomfort, aligning with Cann et al.'s (2014) findings on stress relief.

These coping mechanisms underscore the value of personalized strategies for visually impaired patients. Recognizing and integrating these approaches can help healthcare providers deliver more accessible, patient-centered care, enhancing dignity and emotional well-being (Sousa et al., 2019).

Subtheme 3.4. Venting out emotion

According to Victoria University of Wellington (2023), venting out emotion is defined as expressing and releasing negative emotions as a coping mechanism. This practice is one of the coping mechanisms done by the participants. Some participants had done this through crying when they reflected on their situation and when undergoing uncomfortable interventions.

This coping mechanism could be linked to the study by Tshuma (2022) on how adjustments to certain situations can result in greater self-efficacy, higher self-esteem, lower levels of depression, and a sense of more control. In addition, implementing catharsis in many ways has always been considered therapeutic. This includes how expressing feelings through written text can help enhance mental health (Bukar et al., 2019).

Subtheme 3.5. Optimism amidst the challenges

Optimism amidst challenges is the process of viewing difficult situations in a positive light. Instead of seeing obstacles, optimistic individuals view challenges as temporary hurdles that can be overcome with effort. It involves reframing setbacks as opportunities for growth, learning, and personal development.

The participants' experiences during their hospitalization highlight their unique ways of coping with challenges through optimism amidst the challenges. Their narratives offer insights into maintaining optimism and understanding despite facing difficulties in a hospital setting.

According to Bandura's Self-Efficacy theory, self-efficacy is the belief in one's ability to succeed in a specific task. Individuals with high self-efficacy approach challenges with confidence, while those with low self-efficacy may feel discouraged. Both Orange and Brown demonstrate self-efficacy in their coping strategies, maintaining a positive outlook and confidence in handling their hospitalization challenges.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Hospitalized individuals with visual disabilities face challenges navigating hospital environments due to inaccessible pathways and a lack of assistive devices. These barriers may delay access to amenities and care, highlighting the need for improved orientation aids and accessible hospital designs. Positive healthcare interactions involve care and prompt attention, while negative experiences include delays, inappropriate behavior, and lapses in care. Despite these challenges, visually disabled individuals demonstrate resilience through adaptive strategies. Hence, policymakers should consider prioritizing accessibility in healthcare by conducting regular accessibility audits and providing training for healthcare providers on disability rights and assistive technologies. Aligning these efforts with the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities may help advance inclusivity and equity. Practical measures such as installing tactile graphics, braille signage, and embossed materials could assist visually impaired patients in navigating hospital environments more independently. Collaboration with disability advocacy groups and the development of feedback mechanisms might further support accessibility initiatives. Hospitals are encouraged to explore implementing accessibility standards and providing financial support for inclusive initiatives. Sensitivity and accessibility training for healthcare professionals can significantly enhance patient interactions and care experiences. Offering seminars and workshops on the needs of visually disabled patients may foster better understanding and empathy among health workers.

Additionally, the Persons with Disability Affairs Office (PDAO) could advocate for accessible communication materials, specialized training, and periodic assessments to sustain inclusive practices. Future research is advised to examine the experiences of visually disabled individuals in both government and private hospitals to identify differences in care and communication strategies. Investigating the role of Humanistic Nursing Theory in promoting patient satisfaction and independence, as well as the influence of cultural and socioeconomic factors, could provide insights to inform equitable, patient-centered healthcare programs.

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